

The Variable Voltage Ion Protection Experiment (VVIPRE): Thermospheric and Ionospheric Remote Sensing from the ISS

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ABSTRACT

The Variable Voltage Ion Protection Experiment (VVIPRE) is a demonstration space experiment built by the U.S. Naval Research Laboratory to show how low-cost variable voltage power supplies can protect sensitive spaceflight detectors from space plasma ion damage, extend sensor lifetimes, and deliver high-quality measurements of the Earth's upper atmosphere. Spacecraft charging and ambient ion impingement can cause noise, detector damage, and reduced sensor lifetime on-orbit. VVIPRE variable voltage power supplies compensate for variations in spacecraft potential to reduce or eliminate this unwanted ion flow. Naturally-occurring ultraviolet airglow can then be measured to specify the atmosphere globally. VVIPRE was launched March 15, 2023 to the International Space Station (ISS). The experiment has completed commissioning, is currently collecting airglow data in its default operational mode, and ion detection and rejection tests are on-going. Ultimately, VVIPRE will demonstrate successful ion mitigation by delivering space environment remote sensing data suitable for DoD model use. VVIPRE and its companion Experiment for Characterizing the Lower Ionosphere and Prediction of Sporadic-E (ECLIPSE) form a powerful atmospheric observatory on the ISS.

1. INTRODUCTION

Global-scale information about the space environment and its solar and geomagnetic influenced variation is more important than ever to society and decision makers. The ionosphere is the most variable component of the atmosphere: electron and plasma density can vary by orders of magnitude with respect to local time, latitude, season, solar cycle, and geomagnetic conditions. Ionospheric variability affects numerous civilian and military systems, including high-frequency radio and satellite communications, over-the-horizon radar, Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) and radio navigation, satellite tracking and reentry, surveillance, and precision geolocation.

Space environment sensing from orbit remains the best approach to measure ionospheric and thermospheric conditions around the Earth for global operational models, which provide both nowcast and forecast capability. State-of-the-art space-based ultraviolet sensors can specify both the current ionosphere and thermospheric conditions critical to ionospheric forecasting [Hsu et al., 2014] to feed these data-starved models, and are particularly impactful over poorly-instrumented areas such as oceans. However, remotely sensing the space environment requires very sensitive instruments, which may include as high-gain amplifiers, image intensifiers, and high voltage. Several key daytime remote sensing observations use extreme ultraviolet emissions that require detectors open to the space environment.

Figure 1. Various state-of-the-art space missions, both research and operational, with UV detectors open to the environment have suffered from ambient ion noise that reduced signal-to-noise, data coverage, sensor lifetime, and even led to mission-ending sensor damage, despite ion protection measures.

Typical spacecraft charging and ever-present ambient space plasma can combine to cause noise, detector damage, and reduced sensor lifetime due to ion impingement of UV sensors on orbit (Fig. 1). Heretofore, constant voltage ion rejection has been implemented by numerous space sensors, yet sensors continue to suffer noise, damage, and reduced lifetime [Stephan et al., 2019; Noonan et al., 2016]. Spacecraft charging is a well-known, long-standing challenge for space missions [Garrett, 1981; Anderson, 2012]. In light of the large investment into space sensor missions and with a looming gap in environmental monitoring, a cost-effective solution to this problem is essential. NRL has been at the forefront of analyzing and mitigating this problem, particularly as it affected the Special Sensor Ultraviolet Limb Imager (SSULI) aboard the Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP) operational spacecraft (Fig. 1). The ion damage problem has been attributed to a complex interaction involving the ambient plasma environment at orbital altitude, spacecraft charging and modification of the local plasma environment, and the sensitive sensor itself. Due to wide swings of 10s of volts arising from spacecraft charging over the course of each orbit and highly-variable space plasma density, standard ion rejection grids that rely upon fixed voltages may not sufficiently protect sensors. The solution to this problem is a variable voltage ion protection scheme that can vary over the course of a precession cycle or even each orbit, as needed. By programming variable voltage to compensate for time-variable spacecraft potential, the sensor grid can remain safely above the ambient neutral plasma, excluding the ions that cause sensor damage.

2. EXPERIMENT DESIGN

The VVIPRE demonstration is straightforward: fly a very well-characterized, well-understood sensor with a known sensitivity to ambient ion noise. The Special Sensor Ultraviolet Limb Imager (SSULI) from the canceled DMSP F20 satellite is an exact replica of SSULI sensors that have documented susceptibility to ion noise modulated by spacecraft charging [Dymond et al., 2017]. Operations will take place aboard the ISS, because the ISS platform has known, large swings in vehicle potential. The ISS operates in a plasma-rich environment, not far above the ionospheric peak. The wake-facing Limb-imaging Ionospheric and Thermospheric EUV Spectrograph (LITES) aboard the ISS observed ion noise during its operations, and VVIPRE is similarly oriented.

Figure 2. VVIPRE will orbit aboard the ISS just above the peak of the F-region ionosphere viewing aft. Ion repeller voltages will reject ambient ions that can cause instrumental noise, while allowing UV photons to enter the instrument for remotely sensing the airglow.

Figure 3. The VVIPRE experiment at Kennedy Space Center after refurbishment for the STP-H9 mission. The VVIPRE Ultraviolet Spectrograph Assembly sits atop a nadir plate and wedge to view the aft limb of the International Space Station from the STP-H9 enclosure.

Figure 4. VVIPRE has three separate power supply units attached to ion rejection grids within the sensor: the sun shade (V_1), the collimator grid (V_2), and in front of the detector (V_3). Each power supply is independently programmable.

The VVIPRE instrument was assembled from a refurbished SSULI unit, which included the Ultraviolet Spectrograph Assemble (USA), the SSULI Control Electronics (SCE), and dual detector high voltage power supplies. The VVIPRE Electronics Nexus and Orientation Mount (VENOM) was developed specifically for the STP-H9 mission to meet several requirements. First, VENOM presented standard RS-422 protocols telemetry I/O and 28VDC power to the STP-H9 payload, because the legacy SCE used communication protocols and voltages specialized for DMSP. Second, SSULI was telemetry-limited to 25.6 kbps, and so generated 1-D spectra each second, whereas the ISS data rate is much larger. VENOM bypasses the SCE detector interface entirely and communicates directly with the USA detector electronics to produce 2-D detector images each second. Third, SSULI was oriented differently on the DMSP spacecraft than VVIPRE in the STP-H9 enclosure. Fourth, the three variable voltage power supplies for ion rejection were incorporated into VENOM. Finally, the interface included a Linux-based Beaglebone COTS microcomputer to enable sophisticated scripting and control of VVIPRE.

The primary objectives for this experiment are:

- Demonstrate that variable voltage ion rejection technology protects sensitive spaceflight detectors from space plasma ion damage.
- Demonstrate successful ion mitigation by delivering space environment remote sensing data suitable for DoD model use.

The straightforward steps to achieve these goals are (1) to complete early-orbit checkout, aspect solution, detector characterization, and calibration; (2) to experiment with varying voltages among the three ion repeller grids to optimize the configuration; and (3) to generate and deliver the remote sensing data in a format suitable for global ionospheric models. VVIPRE sustained damage during excessively rigorous pre-flight vibrational testing, so extensive on-orbit testing and calibration are on-going to verify sensor refurbishment and performance. Moreover, establishing a definitive baseline sensor status is important for evaluating any ion noise induced degradation during the mission.

The airglow remote sensing of this sensor is performed using a 0.25 m $f/3$ imaging spectrograph in a near-Wadsworth configuration fed by a planar scan mirror and a stacked grid mechanical

collimator. The detector is a 40-mm 2-D crossed delay line imaging detector behind an CsI-coated stacked microchannel plate (MCP) intensifier. See Dymond et al., 2017 for a complete description of sensor characteristics and operation. The original SSULI instruments coadded all the spatial pixels each second to produce 1-D spectra at each scan mirror limb position to stay within the telemetry allocation. The VVIPRE spectrograph uses the same detector hardware, but can produce full 2-D spectral images every second to provide additional information about detector performance. The VVIPRE data can then be processed and reduced to generate 1-D corrected spectra suitable for model ingestion, compatible with legacy SSULI-type data. These data are received in real-time at NRL from the ISS through the TDRS network.

3. EXPERIMENT STATUS

The VVIPRE was launched to the ISS on March 15, 2023 0:30 UT, with installation flowed by initial power-up on March 20. At the time of this writing, initial check-out and commissioning of VVIPRE has completed, and the experiment is functioning well and providing routine airglow spectra in real-time. All ion voltage rejection grids are currently held at default fixed voltages: 22.6 VDC at the sunshade, 0.0 VDC at the collimator, and 42.0 VDC at the detector entrance. Up to this point no cold plasma ion noise has been observed seen in the airglow spectra, which is expected to exhibit a two-dimensional pattern on the face of the intensified crossed delay line detector [Stephan et al., 2019]. Only uniform noise from particle radiation associated with the South Atlantic Anomaly has been observed. This noise is uniform across the detector face (Fig 5.), because the 4 kV detector voltage and mechanical shielding do not significantly affect the high-energy(megavolt) particles inducing this noise in the detector.

The VVIPRE experiment opened to first light UV radiation on April 21 (Fig 6), and limb scanning began April 24 (Fig. 7). The aspect solution and photometric calibration are on-going, and the instrument has not yet begun experimentation to optimize the ion rejection voltages. Under these initial ion rejection voltages, no evidence of ion noise is seen in the airglow spectra, despite the fact that solar activity is increasing.

Figure 7. VVIPRE limb scans on May 7 00:58-01:31 shows airglow near the nightside terminator. Prominent dayglow lines may be seen, and the transition to a nightglow recombination spectrum. The shift can be seen from 83.4 nm resonant emission from O^+ in the daytime ionosphere (near bin 235) to the O^+e recombination 135.6 and 91.1 nm emissions (bins 93 and 215) of the nighttime ionosphere. The limb scans capture the peaks of both dayglow and nightglow layers in the vertical direction.

During its mission with continued exposure of VVIPRE to airglow spectra, natural aging of the detector will occur. Localized “gain sag” in the vicinity of bright lines, particularly HI 121.6 and OI 130.4 nm, arises from a localized loss of MCP intensifier efficiency. The emission line shapes through the mechanical grid collimator are roughly pyramidal [Budzien et al., 2002], and the burn-in preferentially occurs at the brightest portion of the line in both the spectral and spatial dimension. UV emission burn-in can be observed within a month of exposure to UV (Fig. 8), however, there is no evidence of any accumulated two-dimensional gain sag that would be expected from ion impingement and damage. Since airglow retrievals do not typically use these brightest lines, the practical concern is more moderate gain sag in other portions of the detector, which can be characterized by 2-D detector imagery. Moreover, the VVIPRE high voltage power supplies can step up the voltage as the detector ages to recover MCP intensifier gain as needed and maintain sensitivity over the sensor lifetime.

Fig 8. Two full-day accumulated detector images for May 4 (left) and Jun 4 (right) show the effect of burn-in of the bright 121.5 line and, to lesser extent, the 130.4 nm line (bins 133 and 109). Although the two color scales reflect different accumulated signal magnitude, the depressed signal near the peaks of these lines is clear.

4. SUMMARY

The VVIPRE experiment was launched to the ISS on March 15, 2023, has successfully completed commissioning, and is undergoing aspect solution and calibration. VVIPRE is operating well aboard the ISS and is performing limb scans and remote sensing of the airglow as expected. When calibration is complete, VVIPRE will deliver airglow environmental data in real-time through the TDRS network suitable for DoD global models. Data products include daytime ionosphere, daytime thermosphere, and nighttime ionosphere retrievals. As the ISS precesses through a range of local times. VVIPRE will measure the upper atmosphere on a global-scale to provide information on the state of the atmosphere. This is complementary to data provided by the companion ECLIPSE experiment, which volumetrically samples two emission features to provide a detailed picture of daytime metal ions and nighttime ionosphere. The details provided by ECLIPSE combined with the broad context available from VVIPRE are expected to yield new insights into the state of the global ionosphere.

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